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EDITORIAL

EXPANDING EDUCATIONAL SCHOLARSHIP IN MEDICAL SCIENCES

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As far as academics in medicine is concerned, teaching plays a pivotal role. Lot of emphasis is given on content and presentation of teaching. Currently, plethora of faculty development programs are being conducted on how and what to teach. Though faculty spend maximum time and energy in teaching and making students learn, 'teaching' as such is not taken into consideration for promotions of faculty ie. it is not considered as 'scholarly' activity. Rather, our system depends only on teaching experience and publications and research for promotions. As a result, faculty does not get recognition they deserve for teaching, thus restricting their creativity.

It is presumed that to be a 'scholar', is to be a researcher and the yardstick by which scholarly activity is measured is via publications/presentations of research. The idea that only research and resulting publications should be taken into consideration for promotion or recognition needs to be changed.

It's high time scholarly activities other than research, like teaching, are given their due importance. We need to recognize and appreciate all types of scholarships.

Teaching is just an 'activity' carried out by all academicians. For it to be recognized as 'scholarly', certain criteria should be followed to make it more robust.

Scholarship is a term used to demonstrate when knowledge is transformed and dissipated in public after quality assessment and peer review¹.

According to Boyer², 'The richness of faculty should be celebrated'. He emphasized the need for a more inclusive meaning of what it means to be a scholar- knowledge can be acquired not only through research, but also through synthesis, practice and teaching.

According to Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) "Any material, product or resource originally developed to fulfil a specific educational purpose that has been successfully peer reviewed and is subsequently made public through appropriate dissemination for use by others is called a scholarship."³.

Boyer² proposed a model of educational scholarship in 1990, expanding traditional definition of scholarship into four types:

* Scholarship of teaching: Teaching is considered to be scholarship when it demonstrates current knowledge of field, invites peer review and involves exploration of students' learning⁴. It also includes knowledge being made public and presented in a way that others can build upon it.

Examples of scholarship of teaching include development and dissipation of new curricula, course contents, projects, educational videos, book chapters or other teaching materials.

* Scholarship of discovery: It includes funded research projects, publications in reputed peer reviewed journals, book chapters, presentations.

* Scholarship of integration includes: Meta-analysis, professional development workshops, presentation of multidisciplinary scholarly academic works.

* Scholarship of application: This includes all works that help in application of theory into real practice.

All types of scholarships are interring related and the common factor which binds them is transformation and enhancement of activities.

Criteria for scholarship are:

The resource/material should be:

* Peer reviewed- Verified & Valued by those outside of the local context.

* Public knowledge- should be documented, archived, should be accessible and retrievable.

* Platform that can be built upon, replicated & elaborated on, has impact on discipline or community of practice, should be novel, innovative, creative, confirmatory.

* Process should be in scholarly manner.

* Product should require high level of expertise.

By expanding the definition of scholarship criteria, we can include and motivate all faculty who are involved in academic activities other than research⁵. Result would be development of quality enduring products/materials which would be helpful to students as well as other faculty

It is vital to understand that interest and expertise of all teachers/faculty are not same. Some may be better researchers, some better teachers and some better administrators. We need an inclusive system of recognition and reward for diverse faculty so that our system can have maximum benefit, especially at a time when we are in process of introducing new Competency Based Curriculum.

References:

1. Hansen PA, Roberts KB. Putting teaching back at the center. *Teach Learn Med.* 1992; 4:136–9.
2. Boyer, E. L. (1990), *Scholarship reconsidered: Priorities of the professoriate.* (PDF), Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching.
3. Rimal HS. Educational scholarships: The need of today *BJHS* 2017, 2(1)2: 91-92
4. Hutchings P, Shulman LS. The scholarship of teaching new elaborations and developments. *Change.* 1999; Sept/Oct:11–5.
5. Chacko TV. Improving quality of medical education in India: The need to value and recognize academic scholarship. *J Pharmacol Pharmacother* 2013; 4:171-3